

Analysis of Factorial Function for Non-Negative Real Numbers

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Abstract: The real numbers between any two non-negative integers are positive and infinite. This paper analyzes the numerical values of factorial function between any two non-negative integers. This analysis can help to find and correct the numerical error computed by the gamma function.

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1. Introduction

The factorial function [1-3] to positive integer n , denoted by $n!$, is the product of all positive integers less than or equal to n . The gamma function [4-6] is a generalization of the factorial function to positive real values, introduced by the Swiss mathematician Leonhard Euler in the 18th century.

$$\begin{aligned}\Gamma(n+1) &= n(n-1)! = n\Gamma(n). \\ \Gamma(1) = 0! &= 1; \Gamma(2) = 1! = 1; \Gamma(3) = 2! = 2. \\ \text{Also, } \Gamma(r) &= (r-1)! = \int_0^{\infty} t^{r-1} e^{-t} dt. \\ \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) &= \left(\frac{1}{2}-1\right)! = \left(-\frac{1}{2}\right)! = \sqrt{\pi}.\end{aligned}$$

2. Error in Calculation using Gamma Function

It is understood that $\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = \left(-\frac{1}{2}\right)! = \sqrt{\pi} \approx 1.77245385091$,

but $\Gamma(3) > \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) > \Gamma(2)$, which is a contradiction.

$$\Gamma\left(\frac{3}{2}\right) = \left(\frac{3}{2}-1\right)\left(\frac{3}{2}-1-1\right)! = \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)\left(-\frac{1}{2}\right)! = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2}.$$

So, $\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)$ is not true and also calculating the value of $\Gamma\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)$ using $\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)$ can not be true. From these results, it is concluded that the calculated values using $\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)$ are not true.

3. Analysis of Factorials for Positive Real Values

The value of factorial for any positive real number between $0! = 1$ and $1! = 1$ must be 1,

$$i. e. \frac{(0+1)}{2} = 0.5 \Rightarrow \frac{(0!+1!)}{2} = 1. \text{ Thus, } (0.5)! = 1.$$

$$\text{Also, } \frac{(0+0.5)}{2} = 0.25 \Rightarrow \frac{(0!+(0.5)!)}{2} = 1. \text{ Thus, } (0.25)! = 1;$$

$$\frac{(0.5 + 1)}{2} = 0.75 \Rightarrow \frac{((0.5)! + 1!)}{2} = 1. \text{ Thus, } (0.75)! = 1; \text{ and so on.}$$

Let us assume that $0. a_1 a_2 a_3 \dots$ and $0. b_1 b_2 b_3 \dots$ denote real numbers between 0 and 1, where $1 > 0. a_1 a_2 a_3 \dots > 0$; $0.5 > 0. b_1 b_2 b_3 \dots > 0$; $9 \geq a_i \geq 0$; $5 > b_1 \geq 0$; $9 \geq b_{i+1} \geq 0$.

Here, $\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{a_i}{10^i} = 0. a_1 a_2 a_3 \dots$ and $\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{a_i}{10^i} = 0. b_1 b_2 b_3 \dots$. Let $m_i = \frac{a_i}{10^i}$ and $n_i = \frac{b_i}{10^i}$.

Then $\left(\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} m_i\right)! = \left(\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} n_i\right)! = 1. \left(\frac{0! + 0!}{2}\right) = 1$. From these facts, we obtain

$$\left\{\frac{0! + (\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} m_i)!}{2}\right\} = \left\{\frac{0! + (\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} n_i)!}{2}\right\} = \left\{\frac{(\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} n_i)! + (0.5)!}{2}\right\} = \left\{\frac{(0.5)! + (0.5)!}{2}\right\} = 1$$

and $\left\{\frac{0! + 1!}{2}\right\} = \left\{\frac{(\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} m_i)! + (\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} n_i)!}{2}\right\} = \left\{\frac{(\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} n_i)! + 1!}{2}\right\} = \left\{\frac{1! + 1!}{2}\right\} = 1$.

Therefore, the numerical values of factorials for positive real numbers between the consecutive integers 0 and 1 must be 1.

Similarly, the numerical values of factorials for positive real numbers between the consecutive integers 4 and 5 must be the values between $4!$ and $5!$, i.e. the values of factorials for positive real numbers between 4 and 5 must be the values between 24 and 120 because of $4! = 24$ and $5! = 120$.

Let n be a positive integers, $n! = r$, and $(n + 1)! = s$. Then, the numerical values of factorials for positive real numbers between the consecutive integers n and $(n + 1)$ must be the values between r and s .

4. Conclusion

This article analyzes the numerical values of factorial function between any two non-negative integers.

References

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